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of zinc from insulin in the form of chelates by these substances⁵. The antirheumatic action of salicylic acid has been attributed to the ability of this compound to complex with heavy metals and there is a positive relationship between the chelating ability and antithyroid activity among the thiouracils⁶. Tetramethylthiuram disulphide, the most active compound against pathogenic fungi, is also a good chelating agent⁷. Several chelating agents as well as their metal complexes have been examined for their antifungal activity⁸⁻¹⁰.

In view of the above findings, the present series of compounds were synthesised to find out the relation between the fungicidal activity and their ability for chelation with metals like copper, cobalt, nickel and zinc. The carboxymethyl and carboxyethyl thioureas were prepared by treatment of aryl isothiocyanates with glycine and β -alanine respectively. The infrared spectra of 1-carboxyethyl-3-*p*-tolyl-2-thiourea showed a sharp strong band at 3390 cm^{-1} (aryl-NH stretching), a broad band around 3200 cm^{-1} (NH stretching of the second NH group), a strong band at 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching), characteristic bands of the benzene ring near 1600 and 1500 cm^{-1} and bands at 985 cm^{-1} , 1255 cm^{-1} and 1545 cm^{-1} due to C=S stretching¹¹. The other compounds in the series showed similar bands in close proximity to those listed above.

Studies on Potential Fungicides

Synthesis of Carboxymethyl and Carboxyethyl Thioureas

B. DASH & S. K. MAHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar

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THE fungicidal action of sulphur containing compounds are well known. Several thiourea derivatives have been successfully screened for antibacterial¹, antifungal,^{2,3} antitubercular and anti-neoplastic⁴ activities. It has been observed that the biological activity of certain organic compounds is related to their ability for complex formation with metal ions. For example, the diabetogenic action of dithiazone, alloxan and oxine results from the removal

Experimental

1-Carboxyethyl-3[-p-chloro-phenyl]2-thioureas: A solution of 8.5 g. (0.05 mole) of *p*-chlorophenylisothiocyanate dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol and 4.45 g. (0.05 mole) of β -alanine in 100 ml. 1*N* NaOH in a 250 ml. conical flask was stirred at room temperature for 48 hr. The solution was filtered, cooled in icebath and acidified with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid. The resulting white solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p.—154°. Yield 80% (Found : S, 12.02; N, 10.64; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$ Cl requires S, 12.38; N, 10.83%).

The carboxymethylthioureas are prepared by the same procedure as given above by taking the corresponding isothiocyanates and glycine. The melting points, yields and analytical data of carboxymethylthioureas and other carboxyethylthioureas are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—1-CARBOXYALKYL-3-SUBSTITUTED-2-THIOUREAS $\text{RNHCSNH}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{COOH}$

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	$n = 1$		% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Calc.	M.P. °C	Yield %	$n = 2$		% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Calc.
				% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Calc.					% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Calc.		
1.	C_6H_5	141	80	14.74	15.23	12.82	13.34						
2.	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	157	85	13.84	14.29	12.02	12.50	130	80	13.23	13.45	11.51	11.77
3.	<i>o</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	155	85	13.78	14.29	12.13	12.50	153	85	13.14	13.45	11.47	11.77
4.	<i>m</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	170	80	13.73	14.29	12.04	12.50	138	80	13.16	13.45	11.42	11.77
5.	<i>p</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	146	85	12.97	13.33	11.25	11.67						
6.	<i>o</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$							145	75	12.32	12.60	10.72	11.03
7.	<i>m</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	160	80	12.91	13.33	11.16	11.67	125	75	12.14	12.60	10.61	11.03
8.	<i>p</i> - BrC_6H_4							156	75	10.15	10.56	8.73	9.24
9.	<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	180	75	12.71	13.08	11.02	11.45						
10.	<i>p</i> - $\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	127	75	12.14	12.60	10.51	11.03						
11.	α -naphthyl	150	70	11.85	12.30	10.22	10.76						
12.	β -naphthyl	162	70	11.92	12.30	10.13	10.76						

Fungicidal test : For fungicidal assay, the method of Montgomery and Moore¹² with a slight modification has been used. All the compounds were tested for toxicity towards *Drechslera nodulosa*. Six of them are found to be quite promising. The percentage of germination of conidia of the above test fungus during 24 hours is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE OF GERMINATION OF CONIDIA OF *DRECHSLERA NODULOSA* AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THE TEST COMPOUNDS

Sl. No.	Name of the compound	% of germination at 50 ppm.	% of germination at 20 ppm.	% of germination in the control
1.	1-Carboxyethyl-3-[<i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl]-2-thiourea.	18	40	95
2.	1-Carboxyethyl-3-[<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl]-2-thiourea.	20	60	95
3.	1-Carboxyethyl-3-[<i>m</i> -tolyl]-2-thiourea.	20	53	100
4.	1-Carboxymethyl-3-[<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl]-2-thiourea.	15	40	100
5.	1-Carboxymethyl-3-[α -naphthyl]-2-thiourea.	5	37	98
6.	1-Carboxymethyl-3-[β -naphthyl]-2-thiourea.	0	20	95

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Studies in Complex formation of metal ions with N-phenyl-N'-2-Thiazolyl Guanidine

W. U. MALIK, P. K. SRIVASTAVA & S. C. MEHRA*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Roorkee, Roorkee

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FROM the existing literature it has been that although the reaction of metals with a number of biguanides¹ have been studied from the different aspects, the reactions with complex derivatives of the type N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine have received little attention.

Their study is important since a few of them have found use in medicine. Four metals of physiological and biological importance, viz., Cu(II), Hg(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI) were therefore chosen to study complex ion formation. Preliminary experiments had shown that Cu(II) form a soluble complex, dark brown in colour while the remaining three, viz., Hg(II), Mo(VI) and W(VI) gave insoluble colourless compounds. Their composition were determined using appropriate physico-chemical technique.

Experimental

Reagents : Mercuric chloride, cupric nitrate (B.D.H.) of A.R. quality were used for the preparation of stock solutions. The strength of these solutions were determined gravimetrically by the usual methods.

Sodium tungstate and ammonium molybdate solution of pH 2.0 were prepared by adding requisite amount of hydrochloric acid. Fresh solutions were always used in order to avoid the effect due to by aging or hydrolysis. The strength of these solutions were determined gravimetrically by the usual methods².

N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl thiazolyl) guanidine solution was prepared in 70% alcohol.

Apparatus :

O.D. measurements were carried out with the help of Bausch and Lomb's 'Spectronic 20'.

Conductometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (K = 44) using dip type conductivity coeff. Measurements were made at 30° ± 0.1° in water thermostat.

Amperometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal polarograph (India) using scalamp galvanometer (W.G.Pye) in external circuit. All measurements were carried out at 25° ± 0.1° in water thermostat. The capillary used has the following characteristics in the open circuit, $t = 3.5$ sec., $m = 5.54$ mg/sec⁻¹, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 3.38$ mg^{2/3} sec.^{-1/6}.

* Present address : 337, Beheripur, Dargai Gali, Bareilly, (U.P.).